

PHYTOTELMATA AND MALARIA PREVALENCE IN SELECTED RURAL COMMUNITIES OF EMUOHA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the possible influences of phytotelmata on the prevalence of malaria in selected rural communities in Emuoha Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria during the rainy season (June - November) of 2019. Existing malaria data sheet from Model Primary Health Centre Ndele, Rumuji and Ibaa (MPHC-N, MPHC-R and MPHC-I) were utilized. *Ex-post factor* design was employed and was aimed at collecting data and analyzing some variables retrospectively without manipulating any of the variables. Wide variation in prevalence of malaria among age groups were observed in GPA 5.56006-10.7727 (81.6670±1.01379), GPB 4.2886-7.3781 (5.8333±0.60093), GPC 2.5367-6.4633 (4.500±0.76376), GPD 7.0258-10.6409 (8.8333±0.70317), GPE 5.0258-8.6409 (6.8333±0.70317), GPF 3.3996-7.9397 (5.6667±0.85192), GPG 5.6219-8.7114 (7.1667±0.60093), GPH 3.5667-7.4633 (5.5000±0.76396) and GPI 6.6814-13.3186 (10.0000±1.29099), respectively. GPA (0-5yrs) with minimum value of 7.500 was recorded in Rumuji (MPHC-R) while its maximum value of 9.333 was recorded in Ibaa (MPHC-I). GPB (6-11yrs) minimum value of 5.333 was recorded in recorded in Ndele (MPHC-N) while its maximum value of 8.000 was recorded in Ibaa. The least prevalence rate of 6.333 in the month of August was recorded in MPHC-N while its maximum value of 8.4444 was recorded in MPHC-I. There was significant spatial heterogeneity in mean variance of the malaria prevalence in GPC at $P < 0.05$ with GPA, GPB, GPD, GPE, GPF, GPH and GPI showing spatial homogeneity at $P < 0.05$, respectively. Findings indicate that the slight increase of the prevalence of malaria during the month of August may have occurred due to the unregulated phytotelmata plants planted proximally at neighborhood, which has the capacity of impounding water that probably serve as repository for mosquito breeding. Thus, phytotelmata (plantain, banana, pineapples, cocoa yam etc.) should always be planted far off from living premises in a bid to control and prevent high rate of malaria prevalence in the selected communities among other recommendations.

Key words: phytotelma, mosquitoes, prevalence, malaria, ecosystem.